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**“An Exploration of the Cause of
Unexplained Elevated Serum B12 in
Clinical Practise”**

An exploration of the cause of unexplained elevated serum B12 in clinical practice

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Summary

Vitamin B12 or cobalamin plays an essential role in normal bodily functioning. Together with the vitamin folate it is involved in erythropoiesis, as well as in the upkeep of neurological and cellular functioning. The concentration of vitamin B12 in serum is an important clinical indicator of an individual's B12 status, and is used as the first-line marker in the clinical diagnosis of vitamin B12 deficiency which can result from a number of inherited or acquired disorders. High serum B12 concentrations in elderly subjects are very unusual, unless they have been treated with intramuscular injections in the form of crystalline B12 in the treatment of B12 deficiency. The normal range for vitamin B12 in human serum is between approximately 120 and 600 pmol/L and 150-820ng/L (95% reference interval). Levels above this reference range have been found, with levels in the high tens of thousands being reported. It has also been reported that at least 8% of samples with extremely high vitamin B12 concentrations contain an immunoglobulin complexed form of circulating B12. This research project aims to investigate 28 serum samples of elderly patients with very high levels of B12, for evidence of Immunoglobulin bound B12 complexes. Using a microbiological assay to determine the serum B12 concentration of the samples, the samples were treated with polyethylene glycol to precipitate non-specific Immunoglobulin complexes, followed by a second microbiological assay of the samples to determine the percentage of B12 precipitated after polyethylene glycol treatment. In 7 of these samples with B12 levels >7000, the mean % B12 precipitated by PEG was 26.37% (ranging from 0-46%). In the remaining 21 samples, the mean % B12 precipitated by PEG was 18.29%. HoloTC levels in these subjects were consistent with high B12 status. This study suggests that some high B12 levels may indeed be a result of antibodies against B12 and its binding proteins. The project will also include a literature review of the incidence and implications of unexplained elevated vitamin B12 in clinical practice.

Key words: Cobalamin; IgG-B12 complex; HoloTC; Assay

Summary word count: 328

Introduction

The largest of the B-complex of vitamins, with a molecular weight of over 1000, vitamin B12 or Cobalamin is primarily incorporated into the human diet from sources of animal produce [12]. The majority of circulating vitamin B12 is transported in the blood complexed to binding proteins, known as haptocorrins (glycoproteins), similar in nature to those secreted by the stomach and salivary glands during absorption of the vitamin in humans [12-6]. The first discovered haptocorin (TC I) transports 80-90% of the circulating B12; the majority of the protein is saturated with B12, known as holo-haptocorin [6]. The second protein, TC II, is a smaller protein transporting only 6-20% of the circulating B12. While the majority of plasma B12 is bound to haptocorin, the biologically active B12 that the cells can utilize in reactions involving the body's only two B12 dependant enzymes, methionine synthase and methylmalonyl-CoA mutase is carried by TC II [12-6]. The importance of TC II is such that deficiency of haptocorin (holo-haptocorin when bound to B12), carrying the majority of B12 has no metabolic sequelae regarding B12 status, whereas absence of transcobalamin causes severe B12 abnormalities [3, 6, 7]. Vitamin B12 deficiency can arise from many disorders and most commonly presents in the form of a megaloblastic anaemia, similar to that seen in overt folate deficiency. Both vitamins are involved in inter-linked intracellular reactions involved in erythropoiesis and in the methylation of important substrates such as myelin basic protein [12]. Inborn disorders resulting in impaired transport or intracellular metabolism of the vitamin, or acquired, usually resulting in impaired absorption can result in cobalamin deficiency [12, 4]. Elevated levels of the metabolites homocysteine and methylmalonic acid can be found in these inherited and acquired disorders as a result of non functioning of the enzymes (mentioned above) that require B12 as a cofactor, but levels of these metabolites will be even higher in disorders of intracellular metabolism [2]. An important comparison to note is that the serum cobalamin level is usually within the reference range due to the problem arising from errors in metabolism, as opposed to errors involving uptake and transport causing serum cobalamin levels to fall [2]. Interruption of B12 and folate metabolism has clinical consequences most often in the form of anaemia, and neuropathy later on resulting from interruption of the methylation cycle [12]. Requests for the measurement of

serum cobalamin concentration are made to detect deficiency of the vitamin. Serum B12 levels are the first line measurement used in the diagnosis of deficiency. In routine laboratory practice however, results above the reference range (such as those assayed in this research project) are more commonly encountered than results below the lower limit as would be consistent with deficiency [4]. It has also been reported that the incidence of elevated B12 occurs almost twice as often as low ones [11]. It was found that the most common clinical association with high B12 concentrations was renal failure, but no cause for high B12 could be identified in many cases and therapy with B12 in cases of deficiency and myeloproliferative diseases (the most dramatic and best studied causes) were rare causes [4, 11]. High cobalamin levels have not been systemically examined and as such, little is known about the prevalence of high levels in clinical practice and what commonly causes them, which leaves the clinician with little guidance about how to respond to such levels when they are encountered [11]. The best known causes such as those mentioned above, appear to be uncommon, even rare, in the usual clinical setting where cobalamin assay is requested by physicians [11]. In view of the major role of TC II-mediated uptake of cobalamin in the kidney, it was of interest to note that it was reported that HoloTC II was proportionately even more elevated than HoloTC I in a cohort of patients with renal failure [11]. Normally, little or no HoloTC II is present in the circulation because HoloTC II delivers its cobalamin to cells and is rapidly cleared, unlike HoloTC I which has a much longer plasma half-life carrying non-biologically active B12 [11]. Since both HoloTC I and HoloTC II are elevated in renal failure due to lack of renal clearance, this is suggestive of a complex interplay of mechanisms maintaining high serum B12 levels, mechanisms of which may largely be unknown [11]. In a separate study, in which renal failure or other known causes of elevated serum B12 were not factors, results showed a significant link between an elevated serum B12 level and mortality in elderly patients suffering from metastatic cancer in its advanced stage, especially if the cancer involved the liver [5]. An important note is that metastatic liver disease may also be a contributing factor to elevated cobalamin and transcobalamin levels as may many other diseases resulting in liver dysfunction, as high levels of each can be indicative of inflammatory activity where the liver is concerned [5]. The link between mortality and elevated serum cobalamin had previously been noted by Carmel and Eisenberg in 1977. They reported that from a group of 24 patients with a high serum B12 level, the median survival time was one month, contrasting significantly with the four month median survival time in 115 patients with normal or low B12 levels [1]. A correlation between elevated B12 and other metastases to the liver or elsewhere were noted also, but no pathophysiological explanation

for this finding could be validated [1]. Elevated concentrations of serum B12 seem to be a strong predictor of mortality in elderly patients suffering from cancer with one third of elderly hospitalised patients having supranormal serum cobalamin levels (>400) [8]. High B12 levels were also reported to be associated with a 4.48 times greater risk (95% CI=2.14-9.89) of mortality in non-cancer patients within the following 90 days [8]. Furthermore, elevated levels of serum B12 due to antibody bound complexes of the vitamin were described in a series of previous reports in which patients had been treated with B12, but this received little attention [10]. The immunoglobulin complex has been proposed to be one with TC bound B12 and previous reports have described patients with B12-TC-Immunoglobulin complexes causing or contributing to an elevated serum B12 concentration [10]. This is extremely important when one considers the wealth of reports implicating vitamin B12 as a strong predictor of mortality in elderly patients. In this project, serum samples with very high levels of B12 will be examined for evidence of IgG bound B12 complexes. The project will explore whether these samples are associated with bio-markers of impaired tissue vitamin B12 status, such as an elevated plasma total homocysteine.

Methods

For experimental analysis anonymous archival samples were available for this project. These samples were originally for analysis of B12 and folate and were part of a project to determine the utility of HoloTC as an alternative method to assess serum vitamin B12 status. A total of 1,539 samples were available with additional data on gender, creatinine, and age and folate status for some subjects. Subsequent samples from this cohort were selected for further analysis; this information is represented on the following flow chart.

Fig. 1.

26 samples with the highest B12 and large sample volume were further analysed for the presence of B12-IgG complexes.

Microbiological Assay

To measure the serum B12 concentration, a microbiological assay was used. B12 dependant bacteria (*Lactobacillus delbrueckii*) were inoculated into a growth medium with analytical samples at the required dilution. This liquid media was incubated at 37 Degrees Celsius for 42 hours. The absorbance was measured at 590nm. To ensure success of the assay the addition of colistin sulphate was necessary to deter the growth of other bacteria.

Measurement of HoloTC

Assay of HoloTC was carried out via the Abbot AxSYM Microparticle Enzyme Immunoassay technology. This assay is a commercial radioimmunoassay, which is standardised with recombinant human HoloTC, and uses intrinsic factor as a binder and ⁵⁷Co-labelled vitamin B12 as a tracer.

Measurement of homocysteine

Total homocysteine was determined using the Abbot IMx instrument. The method used is the FPIA which uses a combination of competitive protein binding and fluorescence polarisation to determine analyte (Hcy) concentration.

Treatment with PEG

PEG precipitation was used as a relatively crude method for precipitating non-specific antibodies in the final 26 samples. A total of 2.4g of PEG 6000 was dissolved in 10ml of 0.9% saline. Then 0.2ml of the sample was added to 0.2ml of PEG, incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes and then centrifuged for 30 minutes at 2000rpm. One QC4C

control was used with saline. Vitamin B12 was assayed in the supernatants using a microbiological assay.

Results

The first objective was to determine serum B12 concentration in (ng/L) in 83 selected high samples. These results are represented on the following histogram. The histogram shows a much larger percentage of people with serum B12 levels approaching 10000, with numbers gradually declining thereafter, and the highest serum concentration reaching 55000 in roughly 2-2.5 percent of people. Serum B12 levels between 3000 and 4000 are the most prevalent occurring in 17 percent of people. The lowest serum B12 levels between 2000 and 3000 were recorded in 2-2.5 percent of people. The median serum B12 concentration these subjects was 3983 (ng/L) ranging from 1485 – 55000.

Fig. 1. Frequency distribution for serum B12 (ng/L) > 1500 in 83 subjects

Median B12 (ng/L)	Range
3983	1485 - 55000

Table 1 represents the details of 83 subjects with B12 concentrations > 1500 (ng/L). There were a much larger number of samples from females compared to males as shown in table (39 - 6). Serum information for 38 samples other than B12 status was not obtainable, as indicated by the column for samples with no information. The median age of females was much older than males at 71 in comparison to 58 for males. The median serum folate level was only slightly higher in females at 5.4 to 5.2 (ug/mL) in males, but with a much broader reference range. Similarly, median serum B12 concentration was slightly higher in females, again with a much broader reference range. As expected creatinine levels were larger in males. The highest levels of B12 were recorded in the 38 unknown samples. The median serum B12 for these samples was 6223, ranging from [1569-55000] as shown.

Table 1

Details of 83 subjects with B12 concentrations > 1500 ng/L

	Male	Female	No information
N	6	39	38
Age (median)	58 [40-85]	71 [2-88]	
Serum folate (µg/mL) median [range]	5.2 [1.7-8.5]	5.4 [1.5-20]	
Creatinine	116 [51-249]	65 [30-187]	
Serum B12 (ng/L)	3170 [2055-7590]	3323 [1485-19300]	6223 [1569-55,000]

In Table 2, details of the final 26 subjects selected with highest B12 levels and largest sample volume for further analysis by PEG were recorded in a similar format to table 1. Out of this final 26, 1 male sample was available, with 7 female samples and 18 unknown. The median age of female samples remained largely the same in the female population at 72 (median age of females in previous table was 71). The age of the final male sample was much older than the median age of the 6 recorded on the previous table. Serum folate in the male sample was lower than the median folate levels of the 7 females. There was also no significant change in folate levels in females in the final 26 and those from table 1 representing the 83 subjects with B12 levels >1500. The level of Creatinine was higher in the male sample, again as expected. B12 levels in these subjects are significantly higher than those in the previous table. The highest levels were again recorded in the unknown samples with a median serum B12 of 17500.

Table 2

Details of final 26 subjects with highest B12 levels and largest sample volume for further analysis by PEG

	Male	Female	No information
N	1	7	18
Age (median)	85	72 [34-88]	
Serum folate ($\mu\text{g/mL}$) median [range]	2.2	5 [2.8-17.2]	
Creatinine	249	64.5	
Serum B12 (ng/L)	7069	8320 [5665-16400]	17500[6372-81100]

Table 3 represents the percentage of B12 precipitated by PEG and values acquired for the metabolite homocysteine and HoloTC levels in control samples. B12 assay has a 10% CV. Repeated QCs and 5 normal B12 sample levels ran within +/- 10% representing no viable change, comparable to 7 of the final 26 selected samples with highest B12 concentration that also showed no significant change after treatment with PEG represented in table 4 below. Serum HoloTC was also within the normal range with an average value of 67.88[10.43] pmol/L shown below, again as expected. Serum homocysteine concentrations were also normal ranging from 10.2- 25.45 (umol/L).

Table 3

Details of B12 concentrations and other metabolites of control samples used pre and post precipitation of B12 by PEG

Sample ID	Serum B12 before PEG pg/ml	Serum B12 after PEG pg/ml	% B12 Precipitated	HoloTC pmol/L	Hcy umol/L
QC 2C (n=1)	351.79	389.62	-10.75	-	-
QC 4C (n=2)	1332.21	1192.43	10.49	-	-
STD 1000pg/ml (n=2)	951.41	944.79	0.70	-	-
Normal 101	480.09	505.8	-5.36	50.20	10.02
Normal 102	426.28	441.46	-3.56	71.18	16.4
Normal 103	376.87	394.72	-4.74	71.48	17.57
Normal 104	346.88	377.48	-8.82	68.78	25.45
Normal 105	370.32	375.98	-1.53	77.76	12.63

Mean HoloTC
67.88[10.43]

Table 4 represents the final data on the 26 subjects with the highest B12 levels and largest serum volume for further analysis. Included in the table is the percentage of B12 precipitated by PEG and serum HoloTC values. The percentage of B12 precipitated ranged from (-8.5-72.4%). HoloTC levels recorded before PEG treatment were high, ranging from (258.2pmol/L - >2560). Plasma homocysteine values were also analysed for these samples with levels ranging from 7.64 to 35.28umol/L.

Table 4

Details of B12 concentrations and other metabolites of final 26 serum samples with highest B12 levels including the percentage of B12 precipitated by PEG and serum HoloTC values

Sample ID	Serum B12 before PEG pg/ml	Serum B12 after PEG pg/ml	% B12 Precipitated	HoloTC pmol/L	tHcy umol/L
34	12000	13023	-8.5	936.7	7.64
86	81100	81600	-0.6	>2560	
87	9568	9586	-0.2		
9	13800	13221	4.2	258.2	
71	62300	59000	5.3	885.7	9.52
12	13500	12459	7.7	346.4	
80	17500	15866	9.3	700.9	13.73
3	7331	6498	11.4	761.7	13.84
4	8320	7355	11.6	943.3	13.84
48	20800	18239	12.3	1041.9	12.1
75	13700	11974	12.6	786.8	9.98
33	7640	6676	12.6	619.2	9.88
56	7254	6221	14.2	814.2	14.43
81	15900	13631	14.3	695.7	15.26
79	20200	17249	14.6	445.6	16.02
70	54100	45600	15.7	947.1	13.72
69	9541	7706	19.2	636.1	9.45
73	11200	8977	19.8	475.8	23.42
43	5665	4134	27.0	261.6	15.40
49	6372	4585	28.0	666.2	21.22
65	12300	8739	28.9	892.9	10.2
36	6583	4640	29.5	1888	19.12
16	16400	10887	33.6	458.5	
50	26700	16575	37.9	477.9	21.03
51	30100	14185	52.9	>2560	35.28
55	34300	9455	72.4	739.5	17.57

Average HoloTC pmol/L
15.36

Discussion

Information on the prevalence of known contributing factors to high serum B12, such as renal impairment, hepatic or myeloproliferative disease in these samples if any was not disclosed, and this may be a contributing factor to the elevated levels of B12, HoloTC and the metabolite homocysteine. There were a much higher number of female samples used in the assays and the results obtained (female samples showing slightly higher results) may just reflect more varying results in the much higher number of female subjects giving a broader range of values; or they may represent an underlying susceptibility of females to higher circulating levels of B12. They may also represent a higher number of female subjects who are susceptible to B12 deficiency as these samples were originally for analysis of B12 and folate, most often carried out in the case of deficiency. There is no evidence to account for these suggestions however.

Table 1, representing the details of the 83 subjects with B12 levels >1500 ng/L, showed that in all cases other than serum creatinine levels, the female population presented with slightly higher serum values for both folate and B12. The median levels of folate were within the normal ranges for both males and females; with the highest value for females ranging from 1.5 upwards to 20ug/mL. High levels of folate in such cases are unusual given the extremely high levels of B12 in all samples and this might suggest a problem with receptor mediated B12 uptake and usage in this female subject. An acquired disorder may also explain this unusually high folate, with another possible explanation being a dietary excess of folate which is not uncommon, more so in elderly patients. A problem with B12 uptake and utilization or the development of an acquired disorder may explain the original request for folate and B12 serum analysis in these samples.

In the case of table 2 representing the final 26 samples with highest serum B12 levels and largest sample volume, the final male sample presented with much lower folate values than the remaining female samples with a serum folate of (2.2ng/mL). This is indicative of a progressing folate deficiency and creatinine levels in this male sample were extremely elevated suggestive of renal insufficiency, which may also have an influence on serum B12

concentration in this sample. Once again, there is no obtainable evidence to definitively suggest this. There was fluctuation in the range of female serum folate values, with the lowest also indicating folate deficiency at (2.8ng/mL), and the highest indicating an excess of serum folate at (17.0ng/mL). Vitamin B12 was higher in females, again perhaps suggesting an underlying susceptibility of elderly females to elevated levels of B12. Once again this is made interesting by the various reports on increased serum B12 being a strong predictor of mortality in elderly patients, perhaps subsequent analysis will show higher mortality rates in female subjects with elevated serum B12. In the case of the 18 unknown samples in this final 26, both folate and B12 levels were staggeringly high, much higher than that of both males and females. No further information on gender or age was obtainable however.

As shown in table 3, serum B12 concentrations were within the normal range as expected in all control samples. B12 assay has a 10% CV and repeated QCs and 5 normal B12 sample levels ran within +/- 10% representing no viable change, comparable to 7 of the final 26 selected samples with highest B12 concentration that also showed little change after treatment with PEG represented in table 4. HoloTC levels were also within the normal range and this is indicative that no antibodies are present in these control samples maintaining elevated serum B12 levels as expected.

The data present in table 4 represents the percentage of B12 precipitated by PEG, and serum HoloTC values of the final 26 samples. The percentage of B12 precipitated ranged from (-8.5-72.4%). HoloTC levels were high, ranging from (258.2pmol/L - >2560). Plasma homocysteine values were also analysed for these samples with levels ranging from 7.64 (normal) to 35.28umol/L (extremely high). Results in the low end of the spectrum for % of B12 precipitated by PEG in 7 samples (<10%), comparable to results obtained from control samples as mentioned, have corresponding high levels of serum HoloTC which may be indicative of hepatic or renal disease accounting for the extremely high levels of both. This may be an explanation for these high values other than the presence of antibody complexes. Homocysteine values for these subjects were normal indicating adequate activity of the vitamin B12 dependant enzymes. HoloTC levels were consistent with high levels of % B12 precipitation by PEG in 19 of these selected samples as were homocysteine values. This is suggestive that some high B12 levels may indeed be maintained as a result of HoloTC-B12-Antibody complexes; in comparison to the results in table 3 representing the control samples used which showed no significant change as expected.

Limitations

Due to various time constraints involving project deadlines, certain experimental limitations must be accounted for when considering the various results obtained throughout the course of this project. The first of which is the fact that serum HoloTC results represented in table 3 and 4 are related to serum B12 levels before the samples were treated with PEG. Thus, further work is needed to determine if HoloTC levels after sample treatment with PEG mirror the decreased levels of serum B12. Secondly, this study is limited in that we have very little information on the subjects. It may be likely that these subjects have been treated with B12. While there are limitations, some samples did respond to treatment with PEG similar to those in a recent report (Jeffrey, Millar et al), and this project confirms and extends this theory by also taking serum HoloTC levels into account.

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